

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PBL TEACHING METHOD FOR TEACHING PRACTICAL ENGLISH IN IPER (INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH)

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ABSTRACT This thesis integrates Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and Instructional System Design principles into English language teaching. The three main purposes of this quasi-experimental study were 1) to develop effective lesson plans based on Problem-Based Learning for teaching English Conversation for a Daily Life Course, 2) to compare the students' pre and post-test scores of the English Conversation Test and learning achievement of the Practical English Course, and 3) to investigate the students' attitudes towards learning through PBL Instruction. The subjects were 40 Pharmacy and industrial pharmacy faculty bachelor's degree students at the institute of pharmaceutical education and research, Yunusabad 19, Campus. They were separated into two groups, namely experimental and control. The results revealed that the PBL teaching method developed from the PBL Model was effective for teaching English Conversation for the Daily Life course according to the modern standard. The students' post-test score of the English Conversation Test was significantly higher than that of the pre-test at the beginning level, and the students' learning achievement score of the experimental group in learning Practical English Course was higher than that of the control group who learned through the traditional teaching method. Finally, students revealed a very positive attitude

towards learning through use of the PBL method. Thus, it can be said that the PBL method in this study is effective and can be used in English language teaching.

Keywords : Problem-based Learning ; English Language Teaching ; English Conversation ; Instructional System Design ;Attitudes, IPER

Introduction

English is, nowadays, an international language, which plays an important role in our lives such as communication in daily life, business, trade, pharmacy, commerce, science and technology, and education. The high level of English competency, therefore, not only benefits many people during their studies, but helps with professional promotion, career development, and further studies. However, it is generally recognized that the approach to the teaching of English in IPER, especially in the regional and new institutes tends to be based on the Grammar Translation Method, in which the teacher's role is to act as an instructor and corrector of errors. The student's role is to do what the teacher says which, therefore, makes students tend to be over-dependent on their teachers and to always think of their teachers as providers of knowledge. This differ with the purpose of the Education Reform Act, which was intended to promote autonomous and lifelong learning. This is confirmed by the study of scientists who state that teachers in Central Asia start English teaching by introducing vocabulary items and grammatical structures, and then they let the students read aloud or repeat the sentences after the teacher. Students read and translate sentence-by-sentence for the whole class, or individually. Moreover, the scholars confirmed the negative effects of the traditional teaching method by stating that this method of teaching is boring which can lead to negative attitudes towards learning English and reduces incentives for active learning, because students cannot reconstruct the message encoded by the writer for the particular purpose intended.

Problem-based learning (PBL) is a student-centered approach in which students learn about a subject by working in groups to solve an open-ended problem. This problem is what drives the motivation and the learning.¹

To deal with the situation mentioned above, the PBL approach is considered as a more suitable tool to enable students to acquire better English communication than learning through traditional teaching methods. PBL is an approach which emphasizes the use of problems to engage students in active and multidisciplinary learning. Students learn how to solve problems through problem-based learning that are ill-structured, open-ended or ambiguous. According to scholars, PBL is focused, experiential learning organized around the investigation, explanation, and resolution of meaningful problems and students work in small collaborative groups and learn what they need to know in order to solve a problem. Moreover, problem-based learning engages students in intriguing, real and relevant intellectual inquiry and allows them to learn from real life situations.

Even though PBL was originally developed in medical and pharmacy schools and has been used in a variety of settings from middle school to professional education, PBL methods, nowadays, has been used in various areas of science and teaching, for example, architecture, economics, engineering, mathematics and law. However, in the humanities, it is still slowly being experimented with, but in language learning it is going at a snail-pace, probably due to the fact that English language is a non-content subject and teachers tend to spend time on the prescriptive aspects of the language. This is evident in the dearth of PBL research published in the field of language teaching. Moreover, this approach is still unfamiliar and rarely found in language teaching pedagogy.

To develop the new teaching method, the research needs the principles for developing instruction effectively and for teaching English conversation systematically. In doing so, the researcher, therefore, decided to integrate the theory

¹ <https://teaching.cornell.edu/teaching-resources/engaging-students/problem-based-learning>

of Instructional System Design (ISD). Instructional system design is a system of procedures for developing educational and training materials or programs in a consistent and reliable pattern. Instructional system design is a creative, active, and iterative complex process. Although the exact origins of the instructional system design (ISD) process can be debated, the writings of Silvern represent an early attempt to apply general systems theory and systems analysis as an approach to solving problems. Silvern was specifically interested in how general systems theory (GST) could be used to create effective and efficient aerospace and military training and published what might be considered the first ISD model. Consequently, the ISD was integrated to PBL in this study to develop the effective teaching method for teaching English conversation courses.

As mentioned earlier, the cooperative learning played an important role in the learning procedures of PBL teaching method. This helped the students obtain a clearer and deeper understanding of each unit and to get the high scores in the learning activities in the PBL lesson plans. This was supported by the study of scholar which states that students indicated that the collaborative nature of PBL increased their level of comfort and inclusion in the class. In addition, students believed that their learning was enhanced because PBL increased their ability to consider, evaluate, and respect different points of view. In addition, this was also corroborated by the study of teacher who mentioned that as students work on problems in small groups of four or five, their analyses and results in the acquisition of knowledge and problem-solving skills improve considerably. That was why the students' post-test scores was significantly higher than pre-test score and the learning achievement of the students who learnt through the PBL instruction was higher than those who learnt via the traditional teaching method.

The IPER students had a very positive attitude towards learning through PBL teaching method. The reasons of this circumstance were discussed below:

- **Working in teams.**
- **Managing projects and holding leadership roles.**

- **Oral and written communication.**
- **Self-awareness and evaluation of group processes.**
- **Working independently.**
- **Critical thinking and analysis.**
- **Explaining concepts.**
- **Self-directed learning.**
- **Applying course content to real-world examples.**
- **Researching and information literacy.**
- **Problem solving across disciplines.**

The results of the students' attitudes toward learning through PBL teaching method revealed that all items in the questionnaire were rated in the very positive range. This indicated that the students had a very positive attitude towards learning the Practical English course through PBL teaching method. When taking consideration to each item, it was found that the highest mean score was item which was "Learning through the PBL teaching method enhances my critical and logical thinking and improves our problem-solving skills." This might be related to the activities in PBL teaching method which always encouraged students to use their problem-solving skills to solve many problems in the learning processes. After becoming familiar with the problem-solving process, the students were able to enjoy in learning through PBL teaching method. This is supported by the study of scientist who stated that when students were familiar with solving problems, this resulted in a high score for positive attitudes in learning through the provided teaching method. That was why the students of IPER have shown the very positive attitude towards learning the Practical English course through PBL teaching method.

Conclusion

It could be said that learning through PBL teaching method helped students of IPER to learn more actively and that they always used their problem-solving skills whilst working under the procedures of PBL teaching method, such as analyzing problems, finding the solutions and organizing a presentation to express the

information they have gathered for the assignment. They also designed their own learning through planning, monitoring, problem-solving and finding solutions to the problems they have met for developing their presentations. As they engaged in these activities, students retained information more effectively than studying from the traditional method including reading textbook or only by listening to the teacher as shown by the results of this study. Consequently, it can be concluded that the PBL was suitable for being integrated into English language teaching methods and that PBL teaching method as developed by the researcher is effective and appropriate for implementation into the teaching of English conversation classes. Recommendations: below are some recommendations for implementing PBL in the classroom: 1.Explain all the learning procedures carefully for PBL to students if they are not familiar with this kind of learning. 2.Well-designed questions covering all the learning objectives in each unit should be created. 3. Allow students to select the members for working in their group which will make their group work easier. 4.Set aside a session for the groups to discuss the progress of their research and to provide feedback when necessary.

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